

The Cohesive Force of a Copolymer at Oil/Water Interface

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It was generally believed that Cohesive force or Cohesive surface pressure between the CH_2 groups of the neighbouring hydrocarbon chains does not exist at oil/water interface. In some recent publications, it has been shown that such force exists at oil/water interface in the case of long-chain electrolytes. In the present study, experimental evidence in favour of the latter view has not only been cited but also been extended to polymer systems, which have not yet been studied.

The existence of cohesive force of van der Waals type between the CH_2 groups of neighbouring long chain ions at oil/water (O/W) interface has been shown by Ghosh^{1,2}, but the existence of cohesive force in the case of polymers has not yet been known. In the present communication, an experimental evidence in support of Ghosh's view^{1,2}, extended to polymeric systems, is reported. The sample investigated is a copolymer of 2-vinyl- and 2-methyl, 5-vinyl-pyridinium sulphates.

Davies³ has used the following expression to calculate the 'Cohesive force' or 'Cohesive surface pressure' ($-\pi_s$) at air/water (A/W) interface.

$$-\pi_s = (\pi_{O/W}^0 - \pi_{A/W}) \quad \dots (1)$$

where $\pi_{O/W}$ and $\pi_{A/W}$ represent the experimentally determined values of cohesive surface pressure for a given value of A (area/ion) at O/W and at A/W interfaces respectively. The value of Cohesive surface pressure ($-\pi_s$) thus calculated, may be called as $-\pi_s$ (expt.). Davies³ has also proposed the following empirical equation, omitting the usual negative sign placed before, connecting π_s with A

$$\pi_s = \frac{400 m}{A^{3/2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where m is the effective number of CH_2 group in the chain.

On the basis of van der Waals theory of attraction, Chatteraj and Chatterjee⁴ have deduced the underlying equation

$$\pi_s = a_s/A^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

where a_s is a constant analogous to van der Waals constant for a given thickness. Both Davies³ and Chatteraj *et al.*⁴ have pointed out that when $A < 110 \text{ \AA}^2$, the difference between the values of π_s calculated with those observed becomes more and more marked. To account for this anomaly Chatteraj *et al.*⁴ have suggested that for $A \ll 110 \text{ \AA}^2$, micelles are formed

and their presence at the A/W interface needs correction in the value of A . On the basis of certain plausible assumptions they⁴ have deduced the following expression

$$\pi_s = \frac{a_s}{A_c^2} = \frac{a_s}{A^2} \left[1 - nx + \sqrt{\frac{a's}{as}} \cdot x \right]^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where A_c is the corrected value of A , n represents the aggregation number, x is the fraction of the total molecules in associated form, and a'_s and a_s are constants. From the linear relationship, in equation (3), between π_s and A^{-2} for values of $A > 110 \text{ \AA}^2$, Chatteraj *et al.*⁴ have found out the value of a_s [$a_s = 9 \times 10^4 \text{ dynes} \times \text{cm}^{-1} \times (\text{\AA}^2 \times \text{molecule}^{-1})^2$] for a long-chain electrolyte. According to him⁴, the value of a_s depends on the number of CH_2 groups in the long chain ions. In our experiments, the value of a_s is found to be $8.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dynes} \times \text{cm}^{-1} \times (\text{m}^2 \times \text{mg}^{-1})^2$. If the cohesive force at O/W interface is not zero and the constant for that interface is denoted by a_0 , then according to Ghosh^{1,2},

$$a_s = 8.3 \times 10^{-2} + a_0 \quad \dots (4a)$$

The equilibrium constant (K_m) for the reaction $nM \rightleftharpoons M_n$ can be represented in the following form⁴

$$K_m = \frac{x}{A} \left(\frac{A}{1-nx} \right)^n \quad \dots (5)$$

where M and M_n stand for the molecular weight below the c.m.c. and the micellar weight respectively, whereas n is the aggregation number.

On the basis of standard free energy change per molecule (ΔG^0) associated with micelle formation in presence of electrolytes, Phillips⁵ proposed the following equation for the evaluation of K_m

$$-\frac{\Delta G^0}{kT} = \frac{1}{n} \ln K_m \quad \dots (6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta G^0}{kT} &= \frac{2.3 (\log 3 + 2 \log n)}{n} + \frac{2.3 (n-1)}{n} \log (\text{c.m.c.}) \\ &+ \frac{2.3 (n-p)}{n} \log [x + (\text{c.m.c.})] \quad \dots (7) \end{aligned}$$

where p is the micellar charge, x is the salt concentration, and the other terms have their usual significance. When n is large and x is \gg (c.m.c.), equation (7) reduces to

$$\frac{\Delta G^0}{kT} \cong 2.3 \log (\text{c.m.c.}) + 2.3 \left(1 - \frac{p}{n} \right) \log x \quad \dots (8)$$

As there is micellization of the long chain ions or polymeric ions at A/W interface only and consequently A changes to A_c , the change in the value of $\pi_{A/W}$ due to decrease in the number of long chain ions or polymeric ions per unit area should also be taken into account.

From theoretical considerations, $\pi_{A/W}$ and $\pi_{O/W}$ can be expressed² as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{A/W} &= 2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{SA} \\ \pi_{O/W} &= 2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{SO}\end{aligned}\quad \dots (9)$$

where π_k represents the pressure exerted by long chain ions or polymeric ions due to kinetic energy alone, π_r is the pressure due to electrostatic repulsion, and π_{SA} and π_{SO} are the cohesive surface pressures at A/W and at O/W interfaces respectively. The change ($\Delta\pi_k$) due to micelle formation may be obtained approximately from the following expression² :

$$\Delta\pi_k = \Delta n kT = kT \left(\frac{1}{A} - \frac{1}{A_c} \right) \quad \dots (9a)$$

assuming the simple relation $\pi_k = nkT$ to hold good. Therefore, when $A < 110 \text{ \AA}^2$

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_{O/W} - \pi_{A/W} &= (2\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{SO}) - (2\pi_k - \Delta\pi_k + \pi_r - \pi_{SA}) \\ &= \Delta\pi_k + \pi_{SA} - \pi_{SO} \\ &= \Delta\pi_k + \frac{(8.3 \times 10^{-2}) + a_0}{A_c^2} - \frac{a_0}{A^2}\end{aligned}\quad \dots (9b)$$

The observed and calculated values of the factors involved in equation (9b), taking $a_0 = 2.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dynes} \times \text{cm}^{-1} \times (\text{m}^2 \times \text{mg}^{-1})^2$, are recorded in Table 3.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample investigated (supplied by the Ionac Chemical Company, Birmingham, N.J., U.S.A.) is a copolymer of 2-vinyl- and 2-methyl, 5-vinyl-pyridinium sulphates. The structures of the monomers are given below :

R_1 : Vinyl. R_2 : Sulphate.

All the reagents used are of BDH, AR and E.Merck G.R., qualities.

The reduced viscosity measurements revealed that though the sample behaves as an ionic polymer or a polyelectrolyte in aqueous solution but in 0.1 M sodium sulphate solution characteristics similar to that of rigid polymers are observed⁶.

All the measurements are carried out using 0.1 M sodium sulphate as the solvent.

The c.m.c. of the sample, the micellar weight (M_n), and the micellar charge (p) are evaluated from the light-scattering data^{6,7} in the usual way⁸.

Utilizing a static method, based on slight modification of Wilhelmy plate method, for the measurement of interfacial tensions the molecular weight (M) below the c.m.c. is determined⁹ by the usual procedure¹⁰.

The value of the surface van der Waals constant a_s in equation (4), as calculated from the slope of the straight line by plotting π_s against A^{-2} (not shown), is found to be 8.3×10^{-2} dynes \times cm⁻¹ \times (m² \times mg⁻¹)².

TABLE 1

Micellar weight and equilibrium constant of the copolymer

Critical micelle concentration by light-scattering method.	Critical micelle concentration by interfacial tension method	Micellar weight (M_n)	M at A/W interface	$n \cong \frac{M_n}{M}$	p/n	K_m obtd. from eqn. (6)	K_m obtd. from eqn. (5)
6.70×10^{-6}	6.71×10^{-6}	74300	14690	5	0.22	1.382×10^{-23}	1.100×10^{-23}

TABLE 2

Cohesive surface pressure of the copolymer

Film area (A) in m ² mg ⁻¹ $\times 10^3$	π_s in dynes cm ⁻¹ (expt) using equation (1)	π_s in dynes cm ⁻¹ (calculated) from equation (4)
200	2.1	2.08
150	3.6	3.68
130	4.7	4.90
110	6.0	6.86
90	6.5	10.25
85	6.8	11.35
80	7.0	12.96
75	7.3	14.76
70	7.8	16.70
60	8.5	23.06

DISCUSSION

It is evident, from the data recorded in the Table 2, that for a given value of A , π_s calculated from equation (3) is in good agreement with that found experimentally on the basis of equation (1) as long as $A > 0.11$ m² \times mg⁻¹; but when $A < 0.11$ m² \times mg⁻¹, deviations from aforesaid equation become perceptible due to micellization of copolymer ions at A/W interface.

TABLE 3

Cohesive surface pressure of the copolymer

Film area (<i>A</i>) in $\text{m}^2 \text{mg}^{-1}$ $\times 10^3$	<i>A_c</i> in $\text{m}^2 \text{mg}^{-1}$ $\times 10^3$	$\Delta\pi_k =$ $kT \left(\frac{1}{A} - \frac{1}{A_c} \right)$	$\frac{8.3 \times 10^{-2} + a_0}{A_c^2}$	a_0/A^2	π_s (expt) in dynes cm^{-1}	π_s (calculated) from equation (9b) in dynes $\times \text{cm}^{-1}$
90	112.5	0.9434	8.453	2.96	6.5	6.44
85	108.0	1.0570	9.180	3.32	6.8	6.92
80	105.8	1.2860	9.550	3.75	7.0	7.09
75	103.0	1.5300	10.090	4.44	7.3	7.18
70	100.0	1.8180	10.700	4.90	7.8	7.62
60	93.7	2.7420	12.190	6.67	8.5	8.26

It also appears from the data recorded in Table 3 that the experimental values of π_s as determined on the basis of equation (1) are also in good agreement with those calculated from equation (9b) when $A < 0.11 \text{ m}^2 \times \text{mg}^{-1}$.

The values of surface cohesive pressure, a_0/A^2 , at O/W interface at different values of A are recorded in Table 3 (column 5). The surface cohesive pressure in this case is quite appreciable especially when A is relatively small. The origin of this cohesive pressure is due to the fact that the hydrocarbon groups attached to the copolymer ions are in the aqueous side of the interface and there they can attract similar hydrocarbon groups attached to the neighbouring copolymer ions.

Hence the previously accepted view that at O/W interface cohesive force between the copolymer or polymer ions does not exist is not applicable to the present system.

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